

INVESTIGATE HOW VIDEO-BASED TASKS AFFECT THE LEARNING MOTIVATION OF NON-MAJOR UNDERGRADUATES IN NARRATIVE TENSE LESSONS

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Abstract – *Motivating non-major undergraduates to engage with English grammar has long posed a challenge for language instructors, as learners often perceive grammar as a dry subject. Consequently, educators have employed various pedagogical approaches to facilitate the teaching and learning of grammar. In light of the increasing integration of technology in second language acquisition, numerous strategies have emerged for incorporating digital videos into English language learning and platforms for task implementation. This study delves into the efficacy of video-based tasks in grammar classes for non-major English learners, employing a rigorous quantitative methodology. The researchers conducted semi-structured interviews with 50 students at HCMC University of Technology after lessons on narrative tenses, which incorporated video-based tasks. The results indicate the advantageous use of video-based tasks in teaching and learning grammar. Furthermore, they illuminate the significance of video-based tasks as a pedagogical tool to stimulate learners' intellectual curiosity, enhance their grammar acquisition, and augment the learning process.*

Keywords: *teaching grammar, narrative tenses, video-based tasks*

I. INTRODUCTION

The English language holds significant global prominence, being widely utilised in the domains of science, technology, education, business, and politics. Pendergrass et al. [1] even emphasise the pivotal role of the English language in the academic and professional success of engineering students. Recognising this, Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology (HCMUT) acknowledges the necessity of enhancing the English proficiency of its undergraduate students, given that a considerable portion of the academic resources is presented in English. Furthermore, English is not only a mandatory core subject for all non-major undergraduates but also serves as the medium of instruction in various faculties. As a result, a proficient command of English is imperative for academic accomplishments and for producing internationally qualified professionals to enhance scientific publications, innovation, and technology transfer.

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The English classes at HCMUT, designed for non-major students, focus on enhancing listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, with a strong emphasis on grammar. Wang [2] points out that mastering grammar is a prerequisite to becoming proficient in a language, and grammar instruction also plays a crucial role in language teaching. Despite its significance, students do not commonly favour grammar. The primary challenges encountered by students include confusion regarding rules and tenses, as well as the redundancy associated with traditional paper-based drills and rule explanations. Consequently, the efficacy of conventional grammar teaching methods is under scrutiny, warranting research into alternative approaches.

According to Wright (1976, p.1), cited in Cakir [3], language learners can benefit from a variety of media and visual representations. The use of audiovisual materials at the appropriate time can have a positive impact on language learning. In this regard, videos can be a valuable teaching tool for students studying a second language. However, empirical evidence for the learning outcomes and motivation level in second language (L2) learning contexts, especially in Vietnam, still needs to be provided.

To address this research gap, the researchers are inspired to conduct research on applying video-based tasks to improve students' motivation for grammar practice. The research questions in the present research are as follows:

1. To what extent do video-based tasks enhance learners' motivation in grammar practice?
2. What challenges do students encounter in completing video-based tasks?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The role of motivation in grammar lessons

Motivation in L2 learning

According to Nancy [4], motivation refers to the act or process of motivating individuals to take action. Gardner [5] defines motivation as a mixture of desire and struggle, providing motivation and a rationale for conflicting goals. Similarly, Johnson and Johnson [6] describe motivation as a driving force that motivates individuals toward their desired goals

In the context of language teaching and learning, motivating students to learn English as a foreign language (EFL) has been examined in various studies. Based on Gardner's socio-educational model [6], motivation can be viewed as a combination of three components: effort (the amount of time and motivation devoted to studying), desire (the desire to become proficient in a target language) and affect (the emotional response a learner experiences). In their self-determination theory, Deci and Ryan [7] differentiate between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. Extrinsic motivation emerges from external factors, while intrinsic motivation is derived from within the learners. Learners with intrinsic motivation engage in a task purely for its own sake, as it should be

enjoyable or helpful for them to participate in the activity. In contrast, externally motivated students are encouraged by some external benefits, such as passing an exam or winning a prize. As suggested by Brown [8], fostering intrinsic motivation can be beneficial for foreign language students. When intrinsically motivated, students are more likely to engage deeply with the language learning process and sustain their efforts over time. This contrasts with extrinsic motivation, which may lead to more superficial engagement and a reliance on external rewards.

Motivation in learning grammar for L2 classes

Motivation undeniably serves as a cornerstone in the realm of language learning, particularly when it comes to mastering grammar—a foundational aspect of linguistic competence. Despite the emergence of communicative approaches in language pedagogy, which initially downplayed the centrality of grammar instruction, a closer examination of syllabi reveals that grammar remains a pivotal component of language learning curricula [9]. Pinheiro [10] further underscores the critical role of motivation in grammar learning, emphasising that students must be sufficiently motivated to embark on the journey of mastering L2 grammar. Indeed, without the intrinsic drive to tackle grammatical challenges, students may struggle to overcome obstacles and ultimately fall short of achieving actual linguistic competence. In essence, motivation serves as the catalyst that propels learners toward grammatical proficiency. Consequently, by nurturing a positive and motivating learning environment, educators pave the way for students to unlock their full potential, empowering them to navigate the complexities of grammar with confidence and proficiency.

Getting students motivated requires a teacher to learn how to encourage them. Despite the wealth of strategies available, Nunan [11] suggests that there is no universal method for motivating language learners due to the ever-changing nature of language pedagogy and classroom dynamics. One practical approach proposed to achieve this goal involves the use of video-based tasks. These tasks offer dynamic and interactive learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences, enhance engagement, promote authentic language use, and provide cultural context. Educators can stimulate students' curiosity and create enjoyable and meaningful learning experiences by incorporating multimedia elements, ultimately fostering motivation and facilitating language acquisition.

The use of video-based tasks in grammar practice

Students need to grasp the material they are studying in order to reach their maximum potential. Utilising videos as a learning tool is a method that notably influences students' level of engagement.

Video materials used in L2 learning contexts

"Video" refers to a form of audiovisual media that employs digital technology to generate moving images and accompanying sounds. Denning [12] posits that specialised techniques such as animation and computer graphics enable videos to elucidate complex concepts effectively. A wide array of video content can be integrated into lessons, ranging from authentic sources like television shows, films, documentaries, advertisements, news clips, weather updates, and sports events to entertaining animation clips. Videos can be appreciated for their diversity, user-friendliness, and capacity to spark creativity, primarily serving to pique learners' curiosity and stimulate interest [13]. Furthermore, he underscores the diverse nature of videos, which appeal to multiple senses simultaneously, a quality of paramount importance considering the diverse array of learners and learning styles. In addition to visual and auditory stimuli, videos offer playback controls, transcripts, subtitles, and captions [14]. These features empower students to tailor their viewing experience and enhance the accessibility of video materials.

A video-based task is defined as a set of activities designed, prepared, and manipulated by the teacher to instruct students on a grammar topic.

- Students may be expected to complete specific tasks after viewing a *linear video* - a video which students passively watch from start to finish. Students are encouraged to apply what they have learned and to think critically, so practice serves as a means of reinforcing the concepts taught in the video. These tasks can range from short answers to more complex ones, depending on the difficulty level. They can also be used to assess a student's understanding of the material. Students could, for example, be asked to rewrite a sentence from a video using the new grammar concept. Alternatively, students could be asked to create a poster demonstrating one of the concepts presented in the video as part of a science lesson.
- Through the use of an *interactive video*, students may be able to interact with the content in a more dynamic manner. In this form of media, students have a number of options for influencing or deciding on the content outcome. In this manner, students are able to gain a deeper understanding of the lesson and become more engaged. Additionally, it provides students with the opportunity to practice their problem-solving skills. Take interactive videos on grammar as an example. In these videos, learners can actively participate in their learning through the use of clickable areas, quizzes, and branching scenarios.

The role of videos in the learning process

According to Wright (1976, p.1), cited in Cakir [3], language learners can benefit from a variety of media and styles of visual presentations. To put it simply, all audio-visual materials can help

language learning if used at the right time and in the right way. In the view of Nugent (2005), cited in Smaldino [15], a short video provides maximum flexibility for teachers and significantly impacts students' learning in a specific way.

Since video materials are available in a wide variety of formats, they are an excellent method of exposing language learners to the language used in a wide variety of contexts. Language learners can test their comprehension in scenarios that cannot be realistically simulated in the classroom to improve their language acquisition. Video materials can also allow learners to demonstrate their understanding of the material and engage students actively in the learning process.

Video-based tasks and motivation in grammar lessons

According to Alessi and Trollip [16], several techniques can enhance intrinsic motivation, and videos present an excellent opportunity for teachers to implement these strategies effortlessly in the classroom. Techniques such as challenging learners, arousing curiosity, creating explanatory environments, and adding embellishments can all be effectively utilised through videos.

Additionally, a study by Nunan [17] claims that learners can appreciate the communicative value of grammar items when they are presented within authentic contexts. Contextualised grammar activities and tasks allow students to practice the language more meaningfully and realistically and to develop a better understanding of the language. However, L2 textbooks are often purely involved in teaching specific grammar rules, structures, and patterns, typically presenting them without contextualisation. To enhance students' learning experiences and promote authenticity, videos such as radio programs, television commercials, and movie scenes can be utilised. To put it simply, video-based tasks can serve as a valuable source of grammar practice as they add authenticity to the lessons. Meyer et al. [18] argue that language must be integrated into units to facilitate the learning process, which may prove to be more beneficial than taking long-term, 'isolated' grammar lessons. This approach facilitates the learning process by allowing students to apply grammar concepts in meaningful contexts.

In addition, the majority of L2 students learn the language and its grammar for their careers [16]. Students become more motivated when they are able to retain and apply more information to improve their language proficiency for career prospects. Teaching grammar within authentic contexts and incorporating videos can be highly effective [19] to enhance their academic, vocational, and personal success.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research design

The primary objective of this quantitative study was to evaluate the effectiveness of video-based tasks in enhancing the motivation of L2 learners to engage in grammar practice. A semi-structured

interview is a conversational interview conducted with just one respondent at a time, in which a mixture of closed-ended and open-ended questions is asked, along with follow-up queries regarding the reason and manner [20]. As a result, the semi-structured interview is the most preferred method of data collection when the goal of the research is to better understand the unique perspectives of the participants [21]. It is appropriate to use this interview technique when more open-ended questions require follow-up inquiries, despite its time-consuming nature.

Participants

The research was conducted in the second semester of the school year 2022-2023 with the active involvement of 50 students who were enrolled at HCMUT, primarily in their first or second years. They were all native Vietnamese speakers who had a pre-intermediate level of English proficiency. These students demonstrated their commitment and interest by willingly participating in the research to provide feedback on video-based tasks in their English course. Participants were initially not informed of the research's objectives or processes in order to ensure that data collection would not disrupt lessons, learning outcomes, or students' learning experiences.

Materials for grammar practice

The grammar points covered in the study were narrative structures, explicitly focusing on past simple, past continuous, past perfect tenses, and used to. The instructional materials incorporated two animated videos, namely "Oktapodi" and "Up." These videos were selected based on their relevance to the lesson topic, as they effectively illustrate narrative structures in context. Additionally, they were chosen for their cultural appropriateness and familiarity, ensuring that they align with the cultural values and experiences of the study participants.

Figure 1. The cropped screen from "Oktapod"

Source: <https://en.islcollective.com> [22]

"Oktopodi" is a brief animated film depicting the adventure of two octopi striving to reunite after one is sold at a fish store. This interactive video includes pop-up multiple-choice questions on verb tenses, presented when the clip is paused. During these pauses, students collaborate in small groups of four or five to discuss and select the correct answer. Subsequently, they write their chosen option on a small board and present it to the teacher for evaluation.

Figure 2: The cropped screen from “Up”

Source: <https://www.youtube.com> [23]

The short animation "Up" narrates the romantic tale of a couple deeply in love. Following the linear viewing of the video, students engage in a True/False task comprising 15 items. Some sentences feature the "past simple" tense, while others utilise "used to." Students are tasked with determining the accuracy of each statement and indicating whether it is true or false based on the grammatical structure used in the sentence. This activity aims to reinforce students' comprehension of narrative tenses and their ability to identify and apply appropriate verb forms within context.

Data collection

The data collection phase, meticulously planned and executed, spanned over five weeks. This comprehensive period included three weeks for lesson delivery and class observation, one week for interviews to collect students' opinions, and an additional week for response analysis. Subsequent to receiving grammar instruction, they actively engaged in both paper-based and video-based tasks.

This study utilised a semi-structured interviewing process with the students as a means of establishing an understanding of a partnership between the researchers and the participants. In order to minimise fatigue for both interviewer and respondent, interviews are normally conducted in a range of 20 to 30 minutes [20]. Researchers employed open-ended questions in order to gain a deeper understanding of the perceptions and attitudes of the interviewees and develop a discussion that allowed them to relate their personal experiences to the study topic. Each participant was also asked further questions in order to ensure that their responses were comprehensive. Afterwards, the researchers translated the final extracts from Vietnamese interviews into English and then transcribed the translation into a digital format for further analysis.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

The impact of video-based tasks on learners' motivation in grammar practice

Table 1. Students' perceptions of using video-based tasks in narrative tense lessons

Opinions transcribed from the transcripts	The number of responses
Video-based tasks enhance the authenticity of grammatical lessons.	45
Video-based tasks enhance my motivation and involvement in the learning process.	43
Video-based tasks encompass a wide array of engaging activities.	37
Video-based tasks can capture my attention for more extended periods.	35
Video-based tasks offer a more engaging experience compared to traditional paper-based tasks.	31
Engaging with multimedia content hinders my ability to concentrate on learning	17

The data from Table 1 supports the effectiveness of video-based tasks in sparking enthusiasm for grammar practice among EFL learners. Most respondents reported that videos elevate their engagement, transforming the learning process from a passive activity into an interactive adventure. This enthusiasm is further supported by the perception that videos breathe life into grammar lessons by showcasing real-world applications, aligning with research on the importance of authenticity in language learning [24]. In the view of Larsen-Freeman [25], grammar is a dynamic system. If grammar is not taught in a meaningful, psychologically authentic manner, students will not be able to make effective use of grammar in their conversations.

Additionally, a high number of interviewees found video-based tasks a source of engaging activities, a significant departure from the potentially monotonous nature of traditional paper-based exercises, as highlighted by Stockwell [26]. While video's inherent edge over paper-based tasks in terms of engagement garnered a slightly lower response rate, it is noteworthy that a more significant proportion acknowledged videos' captivating nature, holding their attention for extended periods. This aligns with Mayer's [27] multimedia learning theory, which suggests that well-designed video instruction can enhance focus and retention. According to Keller [28], attention is one of the most significant influences on motivation among learners. From the findings, it is evident that video-based tasks can effectively motivate learners by attracting their attention. Interestingly, a minority number of interviewees expressed concerns about multimedia content being a distraction. However, this potential hurdle appears manageable, possibly mitigated through thoughtful design and implementation of video-based tasks as suggested by Roschelle [29], who explored the importance of instructional scaffolding in multimedia learning environments.

Table 2. Students' evaluations of their grasp of narrative tenses following video-based tasks

Opinions transcribed from the transcripts	The number of responses
I recall retaining valuable information from the instructional videos after the class sessions.	38
I can distinguish between past simple, past continuous, and past perfect tenses.	36
I retain the lessons more effectively and for a longer duration.	35
I can generate precise sentence structures in communicative scenarios set in the past.	24

Table 2 shows the result of the survey regarding the satisfaction attitude of students' grammatical competence/performance. Most students expressed their content with their performance after practising narrative tenses with video-based tasks. The survey results indicate that students have a positive perception of narrative tenses and a high degree of confidence in their ability to convey their ideas in past contexts. This is a significant achievement, as it demonstrates their understanding and application of narrative tenses. Most interviewees reported an improved ability to distinguish between past tenses, a fundamental skill for communication [30].

Nearly half of the interviewees are self-assured about their knowledge acquisition. The critical thing to note is that they demonstrate confidence in their ability, which is essential for the success of the language learning process. According to Deci & Ryan [31], once students recognise how videos can improve grammar performance, their intrinsic motivation is activated.

From the survey, 35 out of 50 students retained details from the video after class. In comparison, half of them reported that after completing video-based assignments, they will recall the lessons for a more extended period and with greater accuracy, corresponding to the correlation between academic achievement and motivation [32]. This improved retention could indirectly boost motivation by fostering a sense of accomplishment and progress, as highlighted by Dörnyei & Otle [33] in their work on the role of achievement in motivation. The results of this study support Baggett's [34] claim that information obtained visually is more memorable. It also supports Jonassen, Peck, and Wilson's [35] argument that students are more capable of remembering video content than expository materials. A mental model can be built better by combining auditory and visual symbols than by only using linguistic information [34]. As a result, video-based tasks can effectively improve learners' retention of information.

Based on these responses, the argument that the video was intrinsically motivating may be supported. The high satisfaction reported by respondents suggests that incorporating videos into grammar practice can enhance students' engagement and motivation. This finding highlights the potential of videos as valuable material for educators to create a positive and enjoyable learning environment, ultimately leading to improved academic outcomes.

The challenges students encounter in completing video-based tasks

As part of the survey, students, the key participants in the learning process, were asked to comment on their challenges when using video-based tasks in grammar lessons. While video-based tasks offer numerous benefits, it is crucial for educators to acknowledge the potential difficulties students might face.

A small number of students in our study reported difficulty understanding video content, likely due to insufficient vocabulary. This highlights the importance of pre-teaching key terms or providing subtitles to bridge vocabulary gaps and ensure comprehension. Beyond vocabulary, a few students expressed concerns about video quality, content engagement, or insufficient screen time. These findings echo previous research, which suggests that videos can be overwhelming if presented too quickly [14]. Similarly, Tuncay [36] found students disengaged with uninteresting or outdated content.

Despite the challenges, the data suggests that video-based tasks hold significant motivational power. Students reported increased enjoyment and learning, potentially due to the intrinsic motivators inherent in engaging video content. Students further explained that videos inspire them to actively participate in post-video discussions. This collaborative learning environment further underscores the potential of video-based tasks to foster comprehension and engaging learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles.

V. LIMITATIONS & IMPLICATIONS

The research underscores the positive impact of video-based tasks on EFL learners' motivation. Intrinsic motivators inherent in engaging video content can ignite a passion for language learning, leading to deeper understanding and improved outcomes. However, educators must carefully consider integration strategies to fully harness this potential.

The key lies in thoughtful video selection. While online resources abound, prioritising age-appropriate videos with clear audio and visuals that align with students' English proficiency and course objectives is paramount. Similarly, video length is crucial, as overly long clips can hinder comprehension and engagement. Beyond material selection, diversifying tasks cater to learners' varied styles and interests. This may involve incorporating collaborative learning activities, such as group discussions or role-playing scenarios inspired by the video content. Additionally, addressing potential comprehension challenges is equally important. Providing pre-viewing activities like vocabulary-building exercises or generating prediction questions can prime students for understanding. Strategically pausing videos for discussions or concept checks also allows for deeper processing and clarification, especially for complex grammar points. Finally, do not underestimate the power of reinforcement. Video-based tasks can be leveraged to assess prior

knowledge through low-stakes quizzes, informing future instruction and connecting existing knowledge with new concepts. Furthermore, videos can seamlessly integrate language review, allowing students to solidify their understanding while focusing on a specific grammatical point. This reinforcement is often overlooked in the pressure to cover extensive syllabus content, but video tasks offer a time-efficient solution, eliminating the need for separate homework assignments.

The study also acknowledges limitations that inform future research recommendations. These include the focus on engineering students with lower English proficiency, limited video selection diversity, and the potential impact of lesson duration when using video instruction. The research primarily focused on teaching narrative tenses, and the relatively small sample size and short experimental treatment may have limited the impact on the dependent variables. Future research should address these limitations by expanding the scope, extending treatment duration, increasing the sample size, and incorporating a wider variety of video materials and activities.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, videos as a pedagogical tool offer numerous advantages for grammar teaching and learning in L2 contexts. Videos with authentic and real-life-oriented content and context enhance learners' motivation and shift negative attitudes, facilitating the absorption and application of grammatical structures in sentence construction. Additionally, audiovisual teaching aids leverage their paralinguistic properties to bridge the gap between conventional textbook language and modern realities. Participants in the study recognise the benefits of video-based grammar lessons, but it is also important to acknowledge potential biases and challenges associated with their implementation. Despite the potential benefits of videos as a teaching tool, Phan and Dubien [37] note that teachers may encounter resistance and scepticism. Nevertheless, this paper serves as a source of inspiration for EFL teachers, prompting reflection on how to integrate video-based tasks in the classroom effectively. A combination of authentic L2 input and grammar instruction can enable educators to effectively address L2 learning goals and foster successful language acquisition prospects.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pendergrass N, Kowalczyk R, Dowd J, Laoulache R. Improving first-year engineering education. *Journal of Engineering Education*. 2001;90(1): 33–41.
- [2] Wang. The necessity of grammar teaching. *English Language Teaching*. 2010;3(2): 78–81.
- [3] Cakir I. The use of video as an audio-visual material in foreign language teaching classrooms. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*. 2006;5(4): 67–72.

- [4] Nancy H S. *Management and Motivation*. Jones and Bartlett Publishers; 2013.
- [5] Gardner R. *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. London: Edward Arnold Ltd; 1985.
- [6] Johnson K., Johnson H. *Encyclopedic dictionary of applied linguistics: A handbook for language teaching*. Blackwell Publishers; 2003.
- [7] Deci E, Ryan R M. *Human autonomy: The basis for true self-esteem*. Efficacy, agency, and self-esteem. Kernis M H (ed.). New York: Plenum Press; 1995. p.31–49.
- [8] Brown H. *Principles of language learning and teaching*. New York: Pearson Education Limited; 2007.
- [9] Thornbury S. *How to teach grammar*. Pearson Education Ltd; 1999.
- [10] Pinheiro F. Designing a writing component for teen courses at a Brazilian language institute. *Teachers as course developers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1996. p.119–150.
- [11] Nunan D. *Language Teaching Methodology: A Textbook for Teacher*. NJ: Prentice Hall; 1991.
- [12] Denning D. *Video in theory and practice: Issues for classroom use and teacher video evaluation*. Available:
https://www.academia.edu/4666293/Video_in_Theory_and_Practice_Issues_for_Classroom_Use_and_Teacher_Video_Evaluation
- [13] Zhu Y F. *Principles and methods in teaching English with multimedia*. Advances in Computer Science and Education. Xie A, Huang X (Eds). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer; 2012. p.135–139.
- [14] Pujola J T. CALLing for help: Researching language learning strategies using help facilities in a web-based multimedia program. *ReCALL*. 2002;14(2): 235–262.
- [15] Smaldino E S, Lowther L D, Russel D J. *Instructional technology and media for learning*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Group; 2011.
- [16] Alessi M S, Trollip R S. *Multimedia for learning: methods and development*. Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon; 2001.
- [17] Nunan D. Teaching grammar in context. *ELT Journal*. 1998;52(2): 101–109.
- [18] Meyer J, Youga J, Flint-Ferguson J. Grammar in context: Why and how. *The English Journal*. 1990;79(1): 66–70.
- [19] Warschauer M, Meskill C. *Technology and second language teaching*. Handbook of undergraduate second language education. Rosenthal W J (ed). Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum; 2000. p.303–318.
- [20] Adams W. Conducting Semi-Structured Interviews. *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation*. Jossey-Bass; 2015. DOI: 10.1002/9781119171386.ch19

- [21] McGrath C, Palmgren P J, Liljedahl M. Twelve tips for conducting qualitative research interviews. *Med Teach*. 2019;41(9): 1002–1006.
- [22] iSL Collective. *Oktapodi – Past tense*. [Internet]. <https://en.islcollective.com/english-esl-video-lessons/grammar-practice/general-grammar-practice/oktapodi-past-tense/344953> [Accessed 10 March 2023].
- [23] YouTube. *Nothing gonna change my love for you – True love*. from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AWKUF7xhuIw> [Accessed 10 March 2023].
- [24] Breen M P. *Learner contributions to language learning: A sociocognitive approach*. Longman; 1987.
- [25] Larsen-Freeman D. *Teaching grammar*. Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language. Celce-Murcia M, Brinton B M, Snow M A. Boston: Heinle Centage Learning; 2014. p.256–270.
- [26] Stockwell G. *Teaching business English*. Routledge; 2008.
- [27] Mayer R. E. *Multimedia learning* (2nd ed.). Routledge; 2014.
- [28] Keller J M. Use of the ARCS model of motivation in teacher training. *ERIC*, ED 288520; 1983.
- [29] Roschelle J. *Learning in interactive environments: Scaffolding, reflection and negotiation*. The future of classroom technology. Dwyer C (ed.) Teachers College Press; 2000. p.63–89.
- [30] Ellis R. *Systemic functional approaches to language learning*. Oxford University Press; 2006.
- [31] Weibell C J. *Principles of learning: 7 principles to guide personalised, student-centred learning in the technology-enhanced, blended learning environment*. 2011. Available: <https://principlesoflearning.wordpress.com>.
- [32] Vu T, Magis-Weinberg L, Jansen B R J, van Atteveldt N, Janssen T W P, Lee N C, van der Maas H L J, Raijmakers M E J, Sachisthal M S M, Meeter M. Motivation-Achievement cycles in learning: A literature review and research agenda. *Educational Psychological Review*. 2022;34(1): 39–71. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-021-09616-7>.
- [33] Dörnyei Z, Oettle S. *Motivation, language learning and young learners*. Oxford University Press; 2015.
- [34] Baggett P. Role of temporal overlap of visual and auditory material in forming dual media associations. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 1984;76(3): 408–417.
- [35] Jonassen D H, Peck K L, Wilson B G. *Learning with technology: A constructivist perspective*. NJ: Prentice; 1999.
- [36] Tuncay H. An integrated skills approach using feature movies at tertiary level. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*. 2014;13(1): 56–63.

[37] Phan Ngoc, Dubien M. *Teaching Grammar to English Language Learners with Video: An Integrative Literature Review on Effectiveness, Perceptions, and Practices*. 2022. <http://doi.org/10.34579/00000564>.